

The Role of Literary Narratives in Developing Emotional Intelligence with reference to Rudyard Kipling's poem, "IF---"

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Abstract:

Literature is a mirror of life, reflecting all human feelings and emotions. We will not be separated from our emotions. Emotions are an inseparable part of humans. We feel, so we are in this world. Emotions are the trigger of life. Emotions can navigate us to be the creator as well as the destroyer. Our emotions and feelings shape our behaviour in social contexts as good human beings. This thought defends the role of literature in our lives. Literature helps people become good, morally and ethically responsible people. The present paper will focus on how literary narratives develop human emotions and help mankind manage them in positive, optimistic ways. On the other hand, I want to focus on the literary narrative, such as poetry, which can lead human beings toward Emotional Intelligence. For this purpose, I have selected poetry as the literary narrative and referred to the poem, "IF---" written by Rudyard Kipling.

Keywords: Literary narratives, emotional intelligence, Rudyard Kipling, etc.

Introduction:

Emotions and Emotional Intelligence:

Emotions are physical and mental states brought on by neurophysiological changes, variously associated with thoughts, feelings, behavioural responses, and a degree of pleasure or displeasure. On the other hand, Goldman defines, "Emotional Intelligence (EI) as the ability to manage our own emotions and understand the emotions of others. There are five key elements to EI: self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills. In his book "Emotional Intelligence" (1995), Daniel Goleman argues that emotions can be studied and that people can be taught to understand and manage their own emotions. Emotional intelligence is also known as emotional quotient or EQ. It is the ability to understand our own emotions, manage them in positive ways to relieve stress, communicate effectively, focus on empathy and overcome challenges and reduce the conflicts in our

relationships. There are four key skills of Emotional Intelligence: Self-management, Self-awareness, Social awareness, and Relationship management. These key skills highlight the concepts of self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills, according to Daniel Goleman's model. He stated that all these abilities can be developed. Using these skills, we can improve our emotional intelligence to be a successful person in both our personal and professional lives and achieve our goals. The same key concept is discussed in Kipling's poem "IF---" in his book Rewards and Fairies (1910) and has become the best example of a philosophy of life.

Rudyard Kipling's poem "IF---" and Emotional Intelligence:

Rudyard Kipling (1865-1936), a Nobel laureate, was born in British India. He was an English journalist, novelist, poet and short-story writer. In his poem "IF," he advises young people

to be successful. This poem is addressed to Kipling's son John. The title itself suggests the unknown possibilities and the uncertainty of life. Kipling advised his son that, in the journey of life, we face many problems and situations in which we are unable to make the right decision, and we lose our patience. In such situations, maintaining inner peace is a difficult task. At this point, the role emotions play is vital. We have to handle the situation while balancing our emotions. Kipling has given a proper sense of the situation of life. The theme of the poem is self-control and a true sense of values and morals, as well as ethical maturity and emotional balance, which are similar key concepts of Emotional Intelligence (EI), such as self-awareness, self-regulation, empathy, resilience, and social responsibility. The greatness of Kipling is reflected in this poem, in which he foresees the problems of the coming generation and offers solutions.

Self-Awareness:

The poem opens with the situation in which we need to maintain self-control and self-confidence, and to know our emotions clearly; this is the core of EI. The lines are:

“If you can keep your head when all about you
Are losing theirs and blaming it on you,”

If you can trust yourself when all men doubt you,
But make allowance for their doubting too;
Kipling states the importance of self-control and self-belief. He conveys that in any worst situation in life, when people blame us, we should not lose our minds and prove ourselves with full confidence. We should be calm and steady, stick to our point, and move ahead. We have to take responsibility for our decisions. These lines teach us to be ready for the arguments raised against us. To handle such situations, we need inner strength and self-awareness rather than insecurity,

arrogance, and hatred. These lines lead us to the path of maturity and self-awareness.

The role of Empathy in Life:

Kipling continues with the human values in the latter part of the poem. In the second part, he discussed the importance of empathy for the good human being. According to Goleman, empathy is “the ability to understand the emotional makeup of other people”. Through the speaker's voice, Kipling advises the necessity of emotional endurance and of facing pain while believing in ourselves rather than seeking revenge or grudges. The following lines reflect this theme, instilling in the reader patience, courage, and strength.

If you can bear to hear the truth you've spoken
Twisted by knaves to make a trap for fools,

Acceptance, Resilience and Emotional Stability:

Life is a mixture of crises and joy; it is full of emptiness and losses. Kipling states here that we should not succumb to the situation. Instead of emotional resilience, we should face loss fully heartedly. The following line states this thought as:

And lose, and start again at your beginnings
And never breathe a word about your loss.”

The above lines suggest that emotions play a vital role in our personality development. We have to accept our failure, have the courage to face it silently and without complaint, and work on it to turn the things that happened into positives.

Emotional Balance & Self-Control:

The poem is full of extreme binaries that engage with life situations, like Triumphs vs. disaster, trust vs. doubt, self-mastery vs. chaos, action vs. reflection, kings vs. crowds, etc. All these actions demand emotional balance. Once we achieve this state of balance, we become steady

and calm and able to make the right decisions. This state of mind focuses on self-control. This is the key aspect of Emotional intelligence. Kipling suggests emotional detachment from all extreme situations of life, advocating inner peace.

“If you can meet with Triumph and Disaster
And treat those two impostors just the same.”

Leadership and Social Behaviour:

Throughout the poem, Kipling advised his son to become a responsible citizen and a complete man. He does not allow his son to be an inward individual; he makes him understand the role and responsibilities of an individual towards society. He teaches him the qualities of a good leader: one who does not discriminate between rich and poor, the powerful and the weak, and who establishes ethical communication. He writes this as,

“If you can talk with crowds and keep your virtue,
Or walk with Kings—nor lose the common touch,”

Kipling concludes that following these virtues leads to strong character and greatness.

“Yours is the Earth and everything that’s in it,
And—which is more—you’ll be a Man, my son!”

Conclusion:

Thus, the above study can focus on how the literary narratives can lead us to the area of Emotional Intelligence in the context of Rudyard Kipling’s poem, “IF---“. This poem can rightly be studied in the context of emotional intelligence. Though it was written at the beginning of the nineteenth century (when the psychological theory of Emotional Intelligence did not yet exist), it can also be applied to today’s modern era. It clearly states the key aspects of emotional intelligence, such as self-control, empathy and social balance. This is the best example of literary narration, which serves as the best medium for teaching morals, values, and virtues to individuals, thereby developing their emotional intelligence.

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